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ЖУРНАЛ ГЕПАТО-ГАСТРОЭНТЕРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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OPTIMIZATION OF IRRITANT INTESTINAL SYNDROME THERAPY

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ANNOTATION

60 children with irritable bowel syndrome were observed, divided into 2 groups: Group I (30 children) received the prebiotic Duphalac and fermented milk mixtures, Group II (30 children) - traditional therapy and adapted fresh mixtures. Shown the effectiveness of Duphalac and fermented milk mixtures in irritable bowel syndrome with constipation and intestinal dysbiosis.

Key words: Children, irritable bowel syndrome, constipation, Duphalac.

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ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ТЕРАПИИ СИНДРОМА РАЗДРАЖЕННОГО КИШЕЧНИКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Наблюдались 60 детей с синдромом раздраженного кишечника, разделенные на 2 группы: I группа (30 детей) получали пребиотик Дюфалак и кисломолочные смеси, II группа (30 детей) – традиционную терапию и адаптированные пресные смеси. Показана эффективность Дюфалака и кисломолочных смесей при синдроме раздраженного кишечника, протекающего с запорами и кишечным дисбиозом.

Ключевые слова: Дети, синдром раздраженного кишечника, запоры, Дюфалак.

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TASIRLANGAN ICHAK SINDROMI TERAPIYASINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH

Tasirlangan ichak sindromi bo'lgan 60 nafar bola 2 guruhga bo'lingan holda kuzatildi: I guruh (30 bola) prebiyotik Dyufalak va nordsutli aralashmalari, II guruh (30 bola) - an'anaviy terapiya va moslashtirilgan yangi aralashmalar. Kabziyat va ichak disbiyoz bilan tasirlangan ichak sindromi uchun Dyufalak va nordsutli aralashmalarining samaradorligi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bolalar, tasirlangan ichak sindromi, kabziyat, Dufalak.

Relevance. One of the leading places in the structure of the pathology of the digestive organs in children is occupied by functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract (gastrointestinal tract), which are more common among young children. With functional disorders, motor function, digestion and absorption of nutrients, the composition of the intestinal microflora and the activity of the immune system change in the absence of organic changes and metabolic abnormalities from the gastrointestinal tract.

According to the literature, the causes of functional disorders are diverse and often lie outside the affected organ and are caused by a violation of the nervous and humoral regulation of the digestive tract [1,6]. All this contributes to the development of dyskinesia disorders and the appearance of functional disorders, the issues of correction of which in children are important to this day [4,5] and remain an urgent problem of pediatricians.

Their pathogenesis involves disorders of neuroendocrine regulation, toxic effects, insufficiency of local blood circulation and factors leading to dystrophic changes in the glandular apparatus and the integumentary epithelium [2].

IBS (irritable bowel syndrome) is a functional disorder of the gastrointestinal tract, the main manifestations of which is a violation of the act of defecation with pain syndrome in the absence of organic diseases of the colon. For the first time, the term "irritable bowel syndrome" was introduced by Peters and Bergen in 1944. IBS combines functional changes of the colon and small intestine [2,4].

IBS is a functional disorder of the motor and secretory function of the intestine, the main manifestations of which are a violation of the act of defecation, accompanied by pain in the absence of organic diseases mainly of the colon without its structural changes. In IBS, abdominal pain and discomfort are associated with changes in the frequency and nature of stool and a decrease in pain and discomfort after defecation [3,5].

Functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract, in particular, irritable bowel syndrome, accompanied by cramping abdominal pain due to intense contractions of the intestinal wall, diarrhea or constipation occur in almost all children, starting from the first months of life and a number of authors consider them physiological [4,5,7].

The purpose of the work. Optimization of therapy for children with irritable bowel syndrome.

Material and methods of research. The case histories were studied and a clinical and bacteriological examination of 60 children under the age of 3 with irritable bowel syndrome who were admitted to the emergency pediatrics department of the Samarkand branch of the Republican Center for Emergency Medical Care was conducted. The clinical study was conducted according to the questionnaire. The qualitative and quantitative composition of the intestinal microbiota of sick children was studied in the bacteriological laboratory according to the generally accepted method of fecal culture developed by R.V. Epstein-Litvak and F.A. Vilshanskaya in the modification of M.A. Akhtamov and co-authors [1]. Isolation and identification of bifidobacteria was carried out according to the generally accepted research methodology, taking into account the degree of fecal dilution and the amount of the sowing dose. The diagnosis of microbial imbalance was carried out according to the methodological recommendations [3].

30 children with irritable bowel syndrome received prebiotic Duphalac in age dosage and fermented milk mixtures (group I), and the remaining 30 patients (group II) received traditional therapy and adapted fresh mixtures.

The results of the study. Diagnostic criteria for IBS were: – recurrent abdominal pain or discomfort for at least 3 days a month for the last 3 months, associated with two or more of the following signs: improvement after defecation; abnormal stool frequency (less than 3 times a week); abnormal stool shape (lumpy/hard stool);

Additional symptoms were: straining during defecation, imperative urge or feeling of incomplete emptying, mucus secretion, rumbling and bloating.

In young children admitted to the hospital with irritable bowel syndrome, constipation of an alimentary nature was most often recorded, resulting from a discrepancy in the volume and (or)

composition of food to the physiological capabilities of the child. The study of anamnesis showed that among the examined 38-63.3% of patients were on mixed and 22-36.7% of children on artificial feeding. The following factors contributed to the development of the disease: unfavorable obstetric history of the mother (24-40.0%), allergic reactions to food (14-23.3%), intestinal infections (22-36.7%), helminthiasis (45-75.0%), hypoxic-ischemic changes of the nervous system (19-31.7%), intrauterine or in the process of childbirth. It was also revealed from the anamnesis that 52-86.7% of children fell ill after a violation of the diet - a change in diet or a meal that did not correspond to the child's age in volume (24-40.0%) or composition (15-25.0%), abuse of carbohydrates (sugar, chocolate), lack of protein in food. In 25-41.7% of children, the cause of constipation was an unbalanced mother's diet and in 8-13.3% - an early transfer to artificial feeding.

The majority of patients had concomitant pathology: anemia in 51-85.0% of cases, rickets was diagnosed in 34-56.7% of patients and every third child had signs of atopic dermatitis.

Mothers of 53-88.3% of patients upon admission to the hospital complained of periodic sudden anxiety and unreasonable crying of the child, lasting about three hours a day for several days, 7-11.7% of patients had episodes of increased irritability or inconsolable crying, ending without obvious reasons. Constipation was present in 43-71.7% of patients, regurgitation in 28-46.7% of cases, bloating in 39-65.0% of patients and anorexia in 18-30.0% of children. The increase in stool that occurs with the onset of a pain attack was noted in 17-28.3% of cases, mucus excretion with feces was present in 11-18.3% of children.

Paroxysmal cramping pains associated with eating were indicated by mothers of 23-38.3% of patients, associated with defecation - in 13-21.7% of cases. Morning pain localized around the navel periodically occurring after the child wakes up was noted in 19-31.7% of children.

In all patients, when studying the intestinal microbiota of children, a deficiency of bifidoflora was revealed: in 20-33.3% of cases, bifidobacteria were sown in $5.1 \cdot 10^7$ and in 40-66.7% of children – in $2.3 \cdot 10^8$ dilution.

Bifidoflora in 9-15% of group I children was determined in $3.6 \cdot 10^7$ dilutions, in 21-35% of patients – in $1.2 \cdot 10^8$, and in group II patients - in 11-18.3% of cases, their level was $1.5 \cdot 10^7$ and in 19-31.7% of patients was determined in $1.1 \cdot 10^8$ dilutions.

Sick children received Duphalac as a drug therapy aimed at eliminating symptoms of gastrointestinal dysfunction.

Nursing mothers whose children were on mixed feeding, nutrition correction was carried out with the exception of products that cause gas formation, it is recommended to raise the head end after feeding the baby, avoid overfeeding the child and do a clockwise abdominal massage before feeding.

To normalize the activity of the gastrointestinal tract, eliminate constipation and intestinal imbalance, prebiotic Duphalac and diet therapy with fermented milk mixtures were recommended for complex treatment of group I patients.

The reason for their appointment was that they are absorbed faster, easily absorbed, normalize intestinal motility, promote the growth of bifidobacteria and lactobacilli. It is known that the restoration of intestinal microflora is carried out with the help of eubiotics.

Choosing a drug for the correction of dysbiotic disorders is a difficult task for a pediatrician. The most optimal choice of step-by-step correction of dysbiotic disorders is a combination of pro- and prebiotics.

As a result of the use of the prebiotic Duphalac and fermented milk mixtures in children of group I, as a result of treatment, flatulence disappeared on the next day, and by the end of 2 days - abdominal pain, the general condition of 49-81.7% of patients improved. By the end of 3 days in the first group of patients, the stool normalized and became regular. In group II, bloating, constipation and bifidoflora deficiency persisted for 1.2 bed days longer.

The number of bifidobacteria increased in all examined by 1-2 orders of magnitude. Bifidoflora in 19-31.7% of group I children treated with Duphalac and fermented milk mixtures was determined in $2.1 \cdot 10^8$ dilution, in 11-18.3% of patients – in $4.3 \cdot 10^9$, and in group II patients - in $3.7 \cdot 10^7$ (in 7-11.7% of children) and in 23-38.3% of cases in $2.6 \cdot 10^8$ dilutions.

The effectiveness of Duphalac therapy in combination with fermented milk mixtures was noted in normalizing the softness of the stool, improving the condition of the baby for a short time.

Conclusions. Thus, the complex treatment of children with irritable bowel syndrome, accompanied by intestinal dysbiosis and constipation,

should begin with the use of the prebiotic Duphalac in combination with fermented milk mixtures that contribute to the restoration of the intestinal microbiota and gastrointestinal tract functions.

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